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DO OUR INDIAN MEDICAL GRADUATES WRITE PRESCRIPTIONS AS PER NATIONAL MEDICAL COUNCIL GUIDELINES?

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ABBREVIATIONS: IMG: Indian medical graduate, NMC: National Medical Commission
MCI: Indian medical council, EMRB: Ethics and Medical Registration Board, WHO World Health Organization

ABSTRACT:

Background:

Drug prescription errors may lead to serious consequences including morbidity and mortality so MCI and now NMC send regular notifications to the medical community to enforce the guidelines for a rational prescription. However, due to unknown reasons, a rational prescription is rare to be seen in practice. So we made a short retrospective study of already written prescriptions and compared them whether they meet 100 % of the criteria of the guideline of NMC.

Objectives:

- 1] To find whether our IGMs write drug prescriptions as per the guidelines of NMC
- 2] If writing drug prescriptions as per guidelines of NMC to what extent:

Research Question:

DO OUR INDIAN MEDICAL GRADUATES WRITE THE PRESCRIPTION AS PER NATIONAL MEDICAL COUNCIL GUIDELINE?

Ho: our IMGs do not prescribe as per national Medical Council guideline.

Ha: our IMG prescribe as per national medical council guideline?

Method:

We reviewed the drafts published on the website of NMC and the Indian gazette. We collected sixty-nine ransom samples of prescriptions written by IMGs and studied them and compared already published latest guidelines of NMC of drug prescription including August 2023 including various parameter ideal and rational prescription like mentioning registration number, patient age, name drugs, capitalised letters or not.... The data was collected in Excel sheet for statistical analysis.

Result:

Major findings can be summarised as follows

From analysis we found that the drug name in capital /their Generic were written in capital in 0 %, doctor' registration number was written in 47 %. Emergency contact number was written in 39%, the patient' name was written in 70 % UNIQUE NMC ID was written in 0%.

Conclusion:

The study concluded that a significant number of prescriptions written by Indian Medical Graduates do not align with the standards set by the National Medical Council (NMC) draft

dated 23-05-2022. To address this issue, the NMC should introduce more promotional strategies and incentive-based approaches to enhance compliance.

Our studies suggest that there are challenges in adherence to standard prescribing guidelines among IMGs. Targeted interventions, including enhanced medical education, continuous professional development, and a stricter enforcement of prescribing standards to ensure patient safety and effective healthcare delivery.

Despite widespread media coverage, prescription writing practices remain substandard.

The penalty-like suspension of medical practice licenses for various durations has been a matter of concern. The Indian Medical Association (IMA) has also raised concerns in support of the Indian Medical Graduates (IMGs). The study found that the key areas requiring attention are the deficiencies in prescriptions, including the **Absence of the registration number, emergency contact number, patient's age, review date, and unique ID/registration number (NMC)**. These aspects should be emphasized, and further education and awareness are necessary to address these gaps. In this context, it is worth mentioning that the Rational prescription writing has been made a core issue in new competency medical education [CBME NMC 2023] and is expected to have a positive outcome. The medical profession also faces a huge challenge regarding the availability of all drugs in generic form in all corners of the country. All higher authority should also see that all generic drugs are available in every corner of the country if the high quality and low-cost generic drug are available. Truly speaking only limited drugs are available in genetic form but it is hoped that all generic drugs will be available easily soon. However, the matter is challenging as we need to change the behaviour of img. Higher medical authorities and medical hospitals, organizations and medical professional associations /societies should make standard operating procedures [SOP] - to see that prescription written by IMG ARE AS NMC GUIDELINES.

KEYWORDS: EMRB, NMC Guidelines, Rational Drug Prescription, Analysis, Indian Medical Graduates, Generic Drugs

INTRODUCTION:

On May 23, 2023, the Ethical and Medical Registration Board (EMRB) of the National Medical Commission (NMC) published a final draft of the Professional Conduct Regulation 2022 on the NMC website. This draft emphasizes the importance of writing rational prescriptions by Indian Medical Graduates (IMGs). The Medical Council of India (2002) had previously stressed the same, including the requirement to write generic drug names in prescriptions. Errors in rational and ideal drug prescriptions contribute significantly to preventable morbidity and mortality, especially due to irrational drug combinations. Recent advancements in information technology (IT) and artificial intelligence (AI) have played a crucial role in preventing prescription errors. However, the availability of such technology in all parts of India remains a challenge. Until then, a simple yet effective approach is ensuring rational prescription writing as a modifiable behavior among IMGs. Following NMC guidelines and adopting ideal prescription-writing practices will not only reduce errors and associated morbidity but also help avoid potential regulatory consequences from the NMC.

In this study, we analyze prescriptions written by randomly selected IMGs in the Kalol and Gandhinagar districts of Gujarat. Our primary objective is to assess compliance with NMC guidelines and recommend strategies for better implementation.

METHOD:

The NMC draft as given in Fig. 1 on EMRB was downloaded from the official website, including the guidelines for writing rational prescriptions. We broke down the components of a rational prescription into specific parameters and entered them into an Excel sheet for analysis. Sixty-nine prescriptions were randomly selected and assessed based on these parameters.

The collected data was analyzed statistically in Microsoft excel to identify gaps in compliance.

Randomly selected sixty-nine prescriptions selected for study and entered in excel document and analysed -studied every parameter of rational prescription mentioned or not in the Excel file. We analyzed the data statistically and found the following.

Guidelines-2

The following template may be used for writing prescriptions rationally

Dr.XXXX		
Registration no: XXX		
Address		
Emergency Contact number:		
Patient name:	Date:	
Age :		
Sex:	Weight :	Height
Diagnosis/Provisional Diagnosis		
Rx		
1. Inj XXX ...mg IV/IMhourly fordays		
2.Tab/ Cap XXXXmg per oral after food three times a day for 3 days		
3.Syrup/suspension XXXX --- ml per oral after food three times a day for 3 days		
4. Oint /gel/cream.... Necessary quantity/finger tip to be applied over the affected area times a day till improvement.		
5. Eye Drops XXXX --- drops to be instilled in the right/left eye every 6 th hourly for 3 days		
Not to be repeated		
To review after 3 days		
Signature (With Seal)		
Name		
Unique ID/Reg.No (NMC)		
Qualification)		

Fig 1 NMC EMRB Rational prescription template

RESULT AND STATISTICAL ANALYSIS:

Major findings can be summarised as follows

From analysis we found that the drug name in capital /their Generic were written in capital in 0 %, doctor' registration number was written in 47 %. Emergency contact number was written in 39%, the patient' name was written in 70 % UNIQUE NMC ID was written in 0%.

Other finding is summarised following tables.

Table 1 showing Parameters Mentioned with NMC Rational Prescription Guidelines

Parameters Mentioned with NMC Rational Prescription Guidelines			
SR. NO.	PARAMETERS	YES (%)	NO(%)
1	Doctor's Name	100	0
2	Registration Number	43	57
3	Address	65	35
4	Emergency Contact Number	39	61
5	Patient Name	65	35
6	Age	70	30
7	Sex	43	57
8	Drugs name capital	0	100
9	Drugs doses	30	70
10	Pharmacological/Generic name	0	100
11	Review Date	52	48
12	Signature	87	13
13	Seal	30	70
14	Unique ID/Reg No (NMC)	26	74
15	Qualification	83	17

Statistical analysis:

T value calculated for this set up was 2.91257E-69tt

RULES OF THUMB. In “big” samples, if we get a t-test bigger than 2, we can usually reject the null at the 0.05 level. This is because in “big” samples, the t-distribution is very similar to the Normal distribution, so about 5% of the distribution is above 1.96 or below -1.96. But as t is bigger than 2, we reject HA and accept H0 that our IMGs do not write the prescription as per national medical council guideline,

PARAMETERS MENTIONED IN PRESCRIPTION either mentioned or not
GRAPH 1 showing parameters mentioned in Prescription

GRAPH 2 showing Patient details mentioned in Prescription

DISCUSSION:

National Medical Commission (NMC) has several guidelines for writing prescriptions, including, use generic names: Prescribe generic names instead of brand names, unless there is a specific reason, write legibly: Write prescriptions in legible capital letters. Type and print: Type and print prescriptions to avoid errors, Avoid unnecessary medications or irrational fixed-dose combination tablets, Educate patients: Educate patients about the equivalence of generic and branded medicines. Some exceptions to the generic name rule include drugs with a narrow therapeutic index, biosimilars, and other similar cases.

The study documented the fact that the prescriptions written by our IMGs are not to the expected outcome. There are still numerous challenges in ensuring rational prescriptions align with the NMC's prescribed format. The NMC regularly circulate the draft and mandatory guidelines of rational prescription to all public print media and other publication information resources like TV, radio.

However, we find very few studies on published data regarding the significant gap between rationality of prescription and real-life prescription practice behaviour. WHO [World Health Organization] has also published similar guidelines for rational prescribing behaviour among all medical doctors at the global level. So Rational Prescription practice needs to be observed by regular monitoring. To add further the NMC has also given due emphasis on rational prescription. The original publication of the medical council has also placed strict emphasis on implementing rational prescriptions in the Code of Medical Ethics Regulations 2002. To ensure rational prescribing practices, the use of generic or pharmacological names in Capital Letters is recommended whenever possible. However, our study did not find a single prescription adhering to this practice. In this context, NMC has emphasized very frequently even upon disputes of Indian medical association. The NMC rightly argue that writing a pharmaceutical name will ensure Patient safety and effective Healthcare delivery. This longstanding habit of not incorporating the Pharmaceutical names in drug prescription will require need more time to change the behaviours and practice. Meanwhile online prescription and E-prescription make the situation more complicated. In this context, AI-based prescription APPLICATIONS will solve some issues if such APPs are developed by responsible drug and pharmacological organizations. Mandatory prescription of generic drugs had created a matter of controversy and debate. The medical profession faces a critical challenge due to the uneven or inconsistent availability of generic drugs across different regions. If generic prescribing is made compulsory, authorities must ensure their widespread availability across the country while maintaining high-quality standards and affordability. Here it can be recommended that higher authorities and stakeholders of major medical hospitals and organizations, and their policymakers should establish a clear Standard Operating Procedures (SOPs) to ensure that prescription writing practices by IMGs aligns with NMC regulations that ultimately will benefit both the doctors and the patients. In this context, it is worth giving a due attention over prescribing while practicing telemedicine. On 23/05/2023, National Medical Commission on behalf of Ethical and Medical Registration Board (EMRB) published a final draft on Professional Conduct Regulation 2022 on NMC website. The draft has elaborately emphasised on the type of the drug to prescribe and what not to prescribe while delivering practice over telemedicine platform. For prescribing on telemedicine, EMRB has classified **four list** group of drugs in drafts and their annexures which are as follows:

1 List O: It will comprise those drugs that are safe to be prescribed through any mode of tele-consultation. i.e. Topical Antibiotics: Some topical

2 List A: These are drugs which can be prescribed during the first consultation **ONLY** in cases of video consultations, and if they are being repeated, prescribed for a re-fill, in case of follow-up consultations

3 List B: Is a list of drugs that RMPs may prescribe for patients during follow-up consultations as add-on drugs, in addition to those drugs that were prescribed during an earlier in-person consultation for the same medical condition **NOT** a new drug for a different medical condition or disease. For e. g. to better control Hypertension, the RMP may prescribe an add-on diuretic to a patient on an anti-hypertensive drug prescribed earlier.

4. List of Prohibited Drugs: These are drugs that RMPs providing consultation via telemedicine **CANNOT prescribe. Narcotic, Psychotropics**

CONCLUSION:

The study concluded that a significant number of prescriptions written by Indian Medical Graduates do not align with the standards set by the National Medical Council (NMC) draft dated 23-05-2022. To address this issue, the NMC should introduce more promotional strategies and incentive-based approaches to enhance compliance.

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